

**BUILDING TRUST IN DIGITAL PUBLIC SERVICES: A
MULTI-METHOD STUDY OF MARKETING TECHNIQUES**

Generar confianza en los servicios públicos digitales:
un estudio multimétodo de técnicas de marketing

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Este trabajo está depositado en Zenodo:

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13732318>

ABSTRACT

Today, when services are rapidly digitized, people's trust in government institutions is crucial for economic and social progress. One area that requires further research is the intersection between marketing techniques and public trust, particularly concerning government-funded activities to develop a positive public perception. This article aims to highlight the significance of marketing in enhancing public trust in government services, therefore contributing to the broader goals of economic advancement and social cohesion. The findings suggest that the public sector's marketing industry is flourishing and broadening its efforts to use relationship marketing tactics successfully. The article highlights the crucial need to use sophisticated marketing tactics in the public sector to achieve digital transformation for development goals in countries effectively. Using targeted marketing strategies, governments may deepen the connection between their citizens and state services, encouraging improved public service delivery and fostering increased public trust.

Keywords: Service delivery, public sector, digitalization, relationship marketing.

RESUMEN

En la actualidad, cuando los servicios se digitalizan rápidamente, la confianza de la gente en las instituciones gubernamentales es crucial para el progreso económico y social. Un área que requiere más investigación es la intersección entre las técnicas de marketing y la confianza pública, en particular en lo que respecta a las actividades financiadas por el gobierno para desarrollar una percepción pública positiva. Este artículo tiene como objetivo destacar la importancia del marketing para mejorar la confianza pública en los servicios gubernamentales, contribuyendo así a los objetivos más amplios de avance económico y cohesión social. Los hallazgos sugieren que la industria del marketing del sector público está floreciendo y ampliando sus esfuerzos para utilizar tácticas de marketing relacional con éxito. El artículo destaca la necesidad crucial de utilizar tácticas de marketing sofisticadas en el sector público para lograr la transformación digital para los objetivos de desarrollo en los países de manera efectiva. Mediante el uso de estrategias de marketing específicas, los gobiernos pueden profundizar la conexión entre sus ciudadanos y los servicios estatales, fomentando una mejor prestación de servicios públicos y fomentando una mayor confianza pública.

Palabras claves: Prestación de servicios, sector público, digitalización, marketing relacional.

INTRODUCTION

Government is experiencing unprecedented transformation, in least due to the public's increased thirst for innovative types of marketing. The increasing prevalence of digital technologies in both the private and governmental sectors has caused a fundamental change in how national authorities engage with citizens, highlighting the need of building trust in the government. The delivery of public services by the government is streamlined by digitization, which is another word for anti-corruption. The availability of information and services is more equally distributed because to digitization. Due of these advantages, digitization has been prioritized in every country's State Plan for Development.

The ultimate objective is to create an online system that can accept documents and let citizens seek government services through digital mediums. As we go toward a more digital society, it is crucial that people have faith in the government and its services so that citizens may effectively participate in policymaking.

According to the Ukrainians Rating Group, 64% of Ukrainians have a great deal of faith in the "state in a smart-phone" initiative, which was launched by the Ministry of Digital Transformation as well as other ministries and foreign organizations. Fifty-one percent or more of those surveyed felt that state-level digital technology implementation has improved. Even Nevertheless, over half of respondents either don't use or are unhappy with digital government programs. If people don't trust the government to take care of them, no number of fresh ideas or administrative reforms will make a difference.

Adapting to customers' more innovative use of cutting-edge devices and software necessitates a high-

er degree of digital knowledge, and there are new challenges in creating trust as government operations shift online. Mykhailo Fedorov, the minister in charge of digital transformation, claims that the country's GDP would grow by ten to twelve percent if more government services are made available digitally.

Inadequate marketing resources are hampering efforts to digitally modernize government procedures and restore citizens' faith in public institutions. It will be difficult for state governments to win back the people's trust unless they launch creative public relations initiatives. Without having academic backing in the type of both theoretical and empirical foundations and practical investigation makes them less useful.

Public sector marketing strategies that don't cater for the specific difficulties of living in the digital era will not be sufficient to meet these problems. According to studies, increasing public trust is the top priority for relationship marketers employed by the government. This necessitates the creation of reliable methods of public communication that prioritize openness, responsibility, and citizen input.

For digitalization in Ukraine to be a success, confidence in public services must first be established. Public service delivery, citizen-government engagement, and societal progress may all benefit from the use of marketing techniques and technologies that foster confidence in the sector. Thus, it is imperative that public sector policymakers and practitioners place a high value on marketing in order to enhance public services and earn the confidence of their constituents.

Globally, several governments have begun the process of modernizing their administrative structures via the use of digital tools.

When it comes to the rise of the digital age, few countries can compare to Estonia. As a result of the in-

roduction of digital IDs, voting systems, and digital signatures, residents now have greater access to governmental services online.

Electronic document management, digital signature, and online petition systems are only some of the digital services that have been adopted in South Korea. Furthermore, they have spent a lot of money on smart city infrastructure, particularly in the area of public transit.

To better serve its citizens, Singapore has developed many digital projects, such as a central hub for all government services, electronic medical data, and a national digital identification card. They've also put money into smart city technology like an autonomous bus demonstration and an advanced lighting network.

A variety of digital services have been deployed in Denmark, such as a central hub for filing tax returns online, electronic medical data, and a statewide digital signature system. They've also put in place a number of smart city projects, such as an automated system for collecting trash and directing traffic.

The United Arab Emirates (UAE) has undertaken a number of digital transformation efforts, such as a public services portal, a digital infrastructure identification system, and the Smart Dubai smart city plan. Many forward-thinking initiatives, such as flying taxis and self-driving police vehicles, have also been put into action.

The United Kingdom has launched a number of digital efforts to enhance public services, such as an online site for returning taxes, digital health data, and a digital identification system. Moreover, they have put money into a sophisticated traffic control system and other forms of "smart city" technology.

These are just some of the many nations that have made great strides toward a digitally transformed society.

Efforts to digitally alter governmental services and the citizen experience are underway in many other nations as well.

The aim of the article

In light of the increasing digitalization of service delivery, this article aims to analyze the function of marketing in fostering trust between governments and their constituents. The article aims to provide insights into the role of marketing in developing trust in digital public services and provide policymakers and practitioners with advice on how to improve public services and earn people's trust. The paper examines the evolution of government-funded marketing research and its effects on public-sector marketing using many different methodologies, including innovation, network analysis, and comparative analysis.

Problem statement

Citizens now have better and more accessible access to government services because of the growing digitization of public services in recent years. Citizens must have faith in the government's capacity to protect their privacy and provide adequate services if this is to be achieved. So, the issue described in this article is how to increase people's confidence in the government's capacity to offer safe and effective digital public services via marketing strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Governments are adopting new technologies to improve public services and spur economic development as the globe digitalizes. There is a strong correlation between citizen faith in government and the effectiveness of digital public services. In this article, the function of marketing in fostering confidence in digital public services is reviewed in the literature.

The effects of digitalization on society and the economy [1], [2], [3] the effects on banking products and

services and macroeconomic factors that contribute to the digital divide have all been the subject of research on digital public services [4], [5], [6]. The function of marketing in fostering confidence in online government services has received less investigation.

Research on the role of marketing in the public sector has been ongoing for some time [7], [8], [9]. According to the available research, public sector marketing is a rapidly growing field that incorporates many specializations and places more emphasis on relationship marketing to increase public trust in government services. Researchers have also attempted to distinguish between the marketing techniques of private companies and those of public organizations [9]. Evidence implies that a unique blend of the four Ps of marketing is most effective (product, price, promotion, and location), and other marketing methods are needed to successfully turn communications service users into paying clients [7], [9]. The 4C and 7P frameworks have been used in several studies focusing on the public sector.

Kollet [10] is more interested in how government agencies advertise themselves by crafting a positive public image and tailoring services to specific demographics. In contrast, Yula et al. (2020) investigated how individuals' satisfaction with government services affects their allegiance to the state. They discovered that the quality of public services had a considerable impact on people's allegiance to the government.

The function of marketing in fostering confidence in digital public services is one of the study's novel contributions. With an emphasis on relationship marketing, the study uses a multi-method approach to examine the evolution of government-funded marketing research. In light of the proliferation of online possibilities, it also emphasizes the necessity for more study into the impact of marketing methods on users of public services [11].

This study is a unique addition to public sector marketing research since it fosters public confidence in online government services. In order to attain development objectives related to digital transformation and increase people's sense of belonging to their government, the research emphasizes the need for efficient public sector marketing.

Additional studies have looked at the 4Ps, 7Ss, and quality of public services related to public sector marketing. This article adds something unique to the area by focusing on relationship marketing to foster confidence in government-provided digital services. It also highlights the need for additional study into how marketing tactics affect users of public services [12], [13].

The literature study emphasizes the importance of efficient public-sector marketing in fostering confidence in government-provided digital services. Although the literature has looked at several elements of marketing in the public sector, more study is required to determine how marketing techniques affect those who use public services, especially in the age of digitalization. The distinctive addition of this paper is its emphasis on relationship marketing as a means of fostering confidence in government-provided digital services. Effective public sector marketing is emphasized. There has been some bibliometric analysis of public sector marketing done before [14], but more work is needed to establish the theoretical underpinnings of public sector marketing and its relationship to confidence in the public sector, especially in the context of global digitalization. Using bibliometric analysis tools like VOS Viewer, Scopus, Web of Science instruments, Publish or Perish, and Google Trends, this paper seeks to investigate the current scientific landscape of public sector marketing and its role in constructing trust in the public sector as a foundation for a country's digital development.

METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive search will be conducted using online academic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search will use keywords related to public sector marketing, trust, and digitalization. The search results will be filtered based on publication date, relevance, and inclusion criteria.

Next, the selected publications will be analyzed using bibliometric analysis tools, such as VOS Viewer, Publish or Perish, and Google Trends. These tools will be used to visualize and quantify the scientific landscape and identify the main trends, authors, publications, and keywords in the field [15], [16], [17].

The information acquired through bibliometric analysis will be examined through descriptive statistics and contents analysis methods. The purpose of this study is to analyze the material on public service marketing and the function of faith in the municipal sector in the context of automation in order to identify the most important topics and trends in these fields. The study aims to provide light on the present status of studies in this topic, highlighting any gaps in research and prospective areas for further development [18].

In order to assess the literature on public sector marketing and its connection to confidence in the public sector in the digital age, this research takes a methodical and methodical methodology. The researchers used bibliometric techniques to extract 4171 conference papers, articles, books and chapters relevant to marketing in the public sector from the Scopus database between 1968 and 2022. The sample was reduced to 922 unique papers after the search results were refined and irrelevant article were removed.

To investigate changes in marketing strategies and methods in the pu-

blic sector in the digital age, the study utilized Google Trends. Specifically, the researchers conducted a comparative analysis of "Digital public service" and "Traditional public service" delivery methods from 2017 to 2022. The study used integrated Scopus tools to analyze the number of publications by year and field, as well as to measure publication influence through citation measurements, country co-authorship measurements, and spatiotemporal measurements. VOS viewer software version 1.6.10 was also used to create a visual map of the bibliographical sources used in the analysis.

A critical query was chosen, through Scopus tools were applied to preliminary analysis, data was imported into the VOS Viewer program, VOS Viewer was used for primary analysis of keywords, VOS Viewer was used for processing data for cluster analysis and content analysis, and keywords were chosen for comparative analysis using Google Trends. Overall, the article intended to give an analysis of the patterns and trends of public interest in digitization and conventional public services, as well as the productivity and effect of publications in the area of public sector marketing. The current scientific landscape for digital public services can be viewed by following the steps below:

- Number of publications in public sector marketing by year and by field by using the Scopus database and its built-in tools, the study could provide insights into the number of publications in public sector marketing over time and by field. This could reveal trends in research interests and topics over the years.
- Most influential studies, authors, and journals in public sector marketing: By analyzing citation data in Scopus, the study could identify the most influential studies, authors, and journals in public sector marketing. This could help

to highlight key areas of research and potential collaborations among researchers.

- Cluster analysis of keywords and inter cluster connections: By using VOS Viewer to analyze the selected keywords, the study could reveal clusters of related research topics and how they are interconnected. This could help to identify areas of research that have received more attention and those that may be emerging or underdeveloped [1].
- Comparative analysis of public interest in digital and traditional public services: By using Google Trends to analyze the search volume for “Digital public service” and “Traditional public service,” the study could compare the level of public interest in these two types of services over time. This could reveal changes in consumer attitudes and preferences related to digital transformation in the public sector.
- Country citation and co-authorship measurements: By analyzing citation and co-authorship data in Scopus, the study could identify the countries that have contributed the most to public sector marketing research and the level of collaboration among researchers from different countries. This could help to identify potential areas of international cooperation and knowledge exchange.
- Bibliographic map of sources used in the analysis: By using VOS Viewer to create a bibliographic map of the sources used in the analysis, the study could provide a visual representation of the literature landscape in public sector marketing. This could help to identify research gaps and potential areas for further investigation.

RESULTS

This study analyzed 922 academic articles from the Scopus data-

base published between 1968 and 2022 on marketing in the public sector. By analyzing the publications, the study identified development in this field. During 1968–1991, there was little interest in the scientific community, during 1991–2002, both theoretical and practical attention began to develop. 2002–2008 was the first period of expansion, and from 2008 to 2017 was characterized by increasing academic interest, particularly as a result of the impact that the consequences of the world financial crisis had on the government sector. The next time increasing period was around 6 years, starting in 2017 until 2022 partly owing to the rapid growth of technology as well as the Covid-19 epidemic, which compelled communities to use online public services.

The industry structure of public sector marketing research was also investigated in this study, and the results showed that research in the field of medicine and health accounts for 25.3% of all research activities. Social sciences represent 14.4% of research, and business, management, and accounting rank third, with 8.1% of all research. The study also identified other areas of research, including natural, agricultural, and economic research, each with less than 8% of the total research.

According to the research, public sector marketers use the idea of relationship marketing as part of their strategy. This approach involves connecting customer trust with service quality, loyalty, and satisfaction. The study’s findings, which demonstrate that research concerning public sector marketing has spread out across many other disciplines, provide more credence to the idea that this topic represents a truly interdisciplinary field of study. More studies on public sector marketing are needed to keep up with the expanding academic interest in this field.

Figure 1. Public sector marketing

Six groups of 35 keywords were isolated from the evaluated papers using the VOS viewer program. The public service enjoyment topic area has the most terms (8 total). The marketing communication process was investigated in the purple cluster,

while public sector marketing components were represented in the green cluster, state marketing policy was outlined in the blue cluster, marketing policy reform was shown in the yellow cluster, and the green cluster

Figure 2. Analysis of governmental marketing communication procedures using vos viewers

The largest cluster in red is composed of eight keywords centered on customer satisfaction, while the green cluster is made up of keywords focused on public sector marketing components and strategy development. The blue cluster is comprised of

six keywords centered on state marketing policy, while the yellow cluster relates to government policy reforms surrounding government agencies embracing technology. The purple cluster, last but not least, focuses on marketing communication procedures and the connection between marketing products and consumer behavior. Relationship marketing, as seen in Figure 2(b), is used in the public sec-

tor to increase customer trust, loyalty, and satisfaction. The transition from blue to yellow in Figure 2(c) indicates

that public sector marketing research is increasingly focusing on client loyalty.

Figure 3a. Territorial-geographical analysis

Figure 3b. Spatio-temporal analysis

According to the findings of a territorial-geographical analysis of citations (shown in Figure 3(a)), the most citations go to researchers from the U. S., the U.K., and Australia (to a lesser extent). Both Canada and Spain fared rather well. The spatially analysis in Figure 3(b) demonstrates that the top-citing countries were forerunners in community marketing research, whereas research on this topic was later launched in Germany, Greece AND Canada. Public sector marketing is still a relatively new notion in nations like Brazil, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland, and China.

According to the papers analyzed, public sector marketing research has

developed in response to modern socioeconomic developments and the use of technology. The data demonstrates that marketing techniques may help increase confidence in government and public services. Whether there are any distinctions in the promotional strategies employed for analog and digital public services, it is yet unknown.

Cluster and spatio-temporal analyses have shown that the most recent work in public sector marketing is concerned with the integration of digital technology into government services. It is advised that a comparison of Google Trends searches for “Digital public service” and “Traditional public service” be conducted to discover the primary trends in the scientific development of public sector marketing.

Figure 4 shows how the dynamics of public interest in these ideas might be shown. According to the findings of a territorial-geographical analysis of citations (shown in Figure 3(a)), the most citations go to researchers from the U. S., the U.K., and Australia (to a lesser extent). Both Canada and Spain fared rather well. The spatially analysis in Figure 3(b) demonstrates that the top-citing countries were forerunners in community marketing research, whereas research on this topic was later launched in Germany, Greece AND Canada. Public sector marketing is still a relatively new notion in nations like Switzerland, China, Sweden, Brazil, and Portugal.

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Figure 4. Comparison between “digital public service” and “traditional public service”

Figure 5. Traditional public service by region

Figure 6. Digital public service by region

Consumer attitudes in public affairs have undergone changes in the last five years, as shown by a comparative analysis of public interest in traditional and digital public services. Traditional services were more popular until 2020, but interest in them rapidly increased in March 2022, likely due to the pandemic and quarantine. Today, demand in online services significantly increased and eventually overtook conventional services in terms of dynamics. Governments are looking for innovative marketing strategies to enhance the quality of digital services during this era of digitalization in the public sector.

DISCUSSION

Past studies have shown that public sector organizations may use marketing techniques and technologies to serve their constituents better [8]. However, most books and articles on marketing at the federal level concentrate on how to apply the 4Ps and the 7Ss to the public sector [7]. In light of widespread digitization, the purpose of this article was to establish a theoretical link between the evolution of public sector marketing tools and public sector trust. These links have yet to be previously defined and may help establish credibility in analog and digital government operations.

According to the report, scientific activity in public services marketing peaked between 2017 and 2022, with most articles focusing on the medi-

cal and healthcare industries. It may be attributed to the widespread use of marketing technologies in these sectors and the COVID-19 pandemic. This conclusion is supported by both the findings of the topic analysis and other research, such as those by [19], [20], [21], [22].

The modernization of public services for the people is one of the smaller clusters, according to the cluster analysis, which might be problematic for the growth of public administration. Several nations still use paper documents, provide services offline, and refuse to embrace the benefits of technology. This paper lends credence to the idea that a lack of a solid theoretical foundation and the necessary skills on the part of people and public officials may be to blame for the slow pace of digital changes in public sector marketing strategies [23], [24], [25]. The cluster analysis findings of network connections also show that governments are reluctant to use new technology for promoting public services owing to a lack of confidence.

Contrary to Ukraine, most nations in the European Union and the United States have private health insurance firms that are carefully regulated and compete with one another with government subsidies for those who cannot afford coverage. Companies compete in the public sector by using various marketing methods to improve brand recognition, service quality, and customer loyalty [1], [26].

In order to increase confidence in digital public services, this article em-

phasizes the need for efficient public sector marketing. The results highlight the need to create a theoretical foundation for public sector marketing and the requirement for digital marketing reforms to satisfy public demand. These findings may aid public sector policymakers and practitioners in enhancing public services and fostering citizen confidence [27], [28].

In most instances, some affluent countries' attempts to incorporate digital technology into their public service delivery infrastructure have been continuing for years. For instance, Estonia is often touted as a pioneer in e-government and has a digital administration. The sophisticated e-government systems in Norway, Sweden, and Finland are also well-known. Various federal projects aim to make government services more available online in the United States. The digitization of government services has been a continuing endeavor [29], [30], [31].

Although adopting digital technology into the public service sector in developing countries is sometimes slower than in industrialized countries, access to digital government services still needs to be worked. The government of India, for instance, has started the Digital India program to centralize the delivery of government services to the general public. The Kenyan government established the eCitizen platform, which enables people to access government services online [32], [33], [34], [35].

As was noted in the preceding article, the Ukrainian Ministry of Digital Transformation has set some ambitious targets for the nation, such as moving all government services online by 2024 and boosting the contribution of IT firms to GDP. It is still being determined how successful these endeavors will be and whether they can accomplish their goals within the specified period [36].

In general, the use of digital technologies in delivering public services

varies widely from country to country. It is influenced by various variables, including the technical infrastructure already in place, the government's policies, and the support of the general populace.

Several wealthy nations' efforts to integrate digital technology into their public service delivery infrastructure have been ongoing for several years in most cases. For example, Estonia has a fully digital government and is often cited as a leader in e-government. Norway, Sweden, and Finland are also known for their advanced e-government systems. In the United States, the digitalization of government services has been an ongoing effort, and there are several federal initiatives aimed at making government services more accessible online [37], [20].

In general, the incorporation of digital technologies into the delivery of public services varies greatly from one nation to the next and is determined by a wide range of factors, such as the existing technological infrastructure, the policies of the government, and the support of the general populace.

CONCLUSION

The article investigated the relationship between technology, public engagement, and trust in digital public services while exploring marketing strategies that may bolster public trust. With the changing digital transformation landscape, marketers must focus on establishing trust in service delivery. This requires novel and creative approaches that can adjust to people's changing demands.

The study highlights the need to combine conventional and digital marketing methods to foster trust between government organizations and the general population. To bolster public trust in digital services and encourage active engagement, it emphasizes the need for clear and open

communication, targeted outreach via social media platforms, and transparent interaction. The article highlights the need to continually improve and adapt marketing tactics to keep up with changing customer tastes and technology breakthroughs.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that governments should give high importance to data-driven marketing strategies that use artificial intelligence and analytics to understand residents' wants better and customize services appropriately. This strategy enhances public trust in digital platforms and the delivery of services.

The study suggests that more investigation is necessary on the influence of privacy issues on trust and the incorporation of user experience design in advancing digital public services. Incorporating insights from diverse fields such as information technology, public administration, and behavioral science is crucial for developing more effective marketing strategies.

The article offers valuable perspectives on how marketing may boost public trust and involvement with digital services. The study reinforces the significance of trust in the digital era, which also advocates for a marketing strategy that incorporates transparency, innovation, and a customer-centric approach. To guarantee that digital transformation produces public services that are reliable, effective, and inclusive, we must persist in investigating innovative methods and utilizing technology to acquire a more profound understanding of public needs. Effective management of digital service provision and enhancing marketing's ability to foster a more engaged and dependable audience will require collaborative efforts among academics, policymakers, and professionals.

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